

Crisis in Higher Education?

Paul T. Durbin¹

Published online: 15 December 2015

Abstract: If there is a crisis in higher education today, how should we respond to it? The polar opposite answers are, either better technical education that would prepare graduates for immediate successful employment; or a broad humanities and social science education, preparing graduates for leadership in democratic societies. Without taking sides in this multi-position debate, I try to show here how both extremes, rightly understood, can contribute to the improvement of democratic societies today.

Keywords: educational crisis, humanities and social sciences, better technical education.

Acknowledgement: This is an original paper that presents personal views of the author(s).

Introduction

If there is a crisis, how should we respond to it?

For an activist philosopher like myself, following in the footsteps of the American Pragmatists William James, John Dewey, and G. H. Mead, there is an urgent need for reform in the American higher education system -- often taken, for example by the European Community, to be the very model for the rest of the world nowadays.

There is widespread criticism, for example from business leaders, that today's university graduates are not adequately prepared to take leadership roles in the real world. They need not only more technical education, but better technical education of a sort that will equip them to take on difficult assignments from day one on the job.

At the other extreme, defenders of the traditional learned disciplines -- not only in the humanities, but also in law and medicine (as just two examples), as these fields were incorporated within higher education in the twentieth century -- claim that the arts and humanities, broadly speaking (that is, sometimes including the

¹ Emeritus Professor, Philosophy Department and Center for Energy and Environmental Policy, University of Delaware, Newark DE 19716 USA. E-Mail: pdurbin@udel.edu

social sciences), are the last, best hope of civilization in a world given over almost entirely to the pursuit of profits and power.

Given the broad range of these sorts of critiques, from one extreme to another, it might seem difficult to focus on a single, dominant crisis, and even more difficult to propose a generic solution -- or at least a general model for solutions (in the plural).

But that is my aim here.

It seems to me that two things are missing, all along this spectrum of critiques. The first is the need for an education that will prepare university students for citizenship; and the second is the need for a kind of activism -- not just within the universities themselves but also in the educated public -- of a constituency for change that is absolutely necessary if there is to be genuine reform.

Education for Citizenship

What I first focus on here is a group of academic reformers who have had something to say about a need for education in citizenship; and the group I have in mind are advocates of interdisciplinary education (and research) in a university world dominated by disciplines and the professional associations associated with them.

One set of such reformers includes those calling for more widespread knowledge of science and engineering among citizens in advanced countries, so that they can participate more knowledgeably in democratic discussions of science and technology policies in a technological society. One such group that is well known -- under the banner of science, technology, and society -- arose amid worries about negative impacts of technological development, for example on the environment; and a key idea was that citizens ought to have more say in decisions that affect them than the technocrats were allowing them. Such issues, in the 1970s, included whether or not to proceed with the nuclear generation of electricity, and if the decision were to be yes, then which communities should bear the brunt of nuclear waste disposal, uranium mining, and related aspects of the nuclear power industry. More recently, similar calls have been issued for a more computer literate citizenry -- all the way to calling for the worldwide dispersion of such technological institutions as the Internet, in order, among other reasons, for citizens in less-developed countries to catch up with the rest of the world in the use of this marvelous new technology.

I would not discount these movements -- indeed, I was long associated with one of the main organizations of this type -- but what I have in mind, when I talk about education for citizenship, goes well beyond the producing of more scientifically and technologically enlightened citizens. Among these groups, the primary concern is not usually with what education for citizenship means in the first place.

The first glimmer of that concern came at the beginning of the twentieth century, when "professional education" was beginning to be introduced into already existent universities in the USA (some, at the time, just called colleges). It was felt then that the new professional fields -- for example, engineering as it was

being transformed from a craft-based into a learned discipline to parallel medicine and the law -- had to earn entry into the universities by proving that the new professional practitioners would benefit from a solid grounding in the traditional liberal arts. Concerns of this sort have, nowadays, very nearly disappeared from the literature in higher education policy. What they have been replaced by, for the most part, is efforts such as core curricula -- some of the best emanating from Harvard University but emulated in many different ways by literally hundreds of other universities in the United States during roughly the last three decades of the twentieth century. Some of the designers of these core curricula, nonetheless, echo the reformers of the early twentieth century in maintaining that the only hope we have today of offering a grounding for career training is in the liberal arts. And for them, the key has almost uniformly been to devise interdisciplinary programs.

One explanation of this phenomenon has been provided by the leading spokesperson for interdisciplinary education, July Thompson Klein, who bases her views (in a masterly survey article (Klein, 1983)) on the rhetoric in the documents offered by interdisciplinarians in defense of their ideal. Klein (1983) says interdisciplinarity has been defended as a tool of integration, convergence, symbiosis, and liberation (from close-mindedness), as some examples. Similarly, Klein (1983) continues, in their attacks on discipline-based university departments, the interdisciplinarians claim that disciplinarians are doing no more than defending their turf or their "empires"; at worst, that they are "authoritatively performing mortuary rites over corpses of dead bodies of knowledge." And Klein (1983) summarizes: whether interdisciplinarians unite under the slogan of "system" or that of "organism," it is (she says) "very clear that the dominant conception of interdisciplinarity is that of a productive art of restoring and discovering the grounds for interdependence and relationship."

On this I agree with Klein. Without some ability to integrate, to relate parts of their education to one another and to the world outside the academy, graduates of even the best universities in the USA (and many governments in other parts of the world today send their best students there) would be no more than well trained technicians. Neither Klein nor I would want to disparage technical education; especially not in our highly technological world. But it is important to remember that technical work requires leadership, coordination, direction, even vision. Where could we expect that to come from if not from graduates of the best universities -- not only in the United States but everywhere in the contemporary world?

Later, Klein put her scholarship to work in a book, *Interdisciplinarity* (Klein, 1990). There she provides a comprehensive survey of interdisciplinary research and education. In a capstone chapter and in her conclusion, Klein surveys almost all the efforts to provide an interdisciplinary core for undergraduate education in the United States. She even samples crucial efforts in other countries, such as Britain, Australia, Denmark, Norway, and Japan. Her conclusions were supported by an earlier survey, in 1986, by William Newell of the Association of Integrative Studies. Newell's book (Newell, 1986) turned up 235 programs. Many were relatively recent

and were located in state universities and even community (or technical) colleges; but there were also interesting examples, for instance, at Brown University, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, and Stanford University. There were also pioneering and well established programs at Columbia University, the University of Chicago, and St. John's College in Annapolis (with another campus in Santa Fe, New Mexico). Both books support the claim that the goal is almost always to revitalize the liberal arts as a key to integrative learning.

Klein and others have now updated scholarship on these issues in a handbook (Klein, 2010; Frodeman, et. al 2010).

The best in-depth account of such a program that I know of (though it's now somewhat dated) is Peter Marsh, ed., *Contesting the Boundaries of Liberal and Professional Education: The Syracuse Experiment* (Marsh, 1988).

The urgency of the need for interdisciplinary problem solving in a technological world has been pointed out many times, but I find particularly compelling a plea made some years ago by a fellow philosopher of technology in Germany, Hans Lenk (1984):

Reasonable criticisms of technological development, of particular technological innovations, of their goals and consequences, issues of values and moral responsibility as these impinge on the socio-cultural situation of technology -- all these are the prerogative not only of humanists but also of social scientists and politicians, of reflective planners and systems analysts, of the technological experts themselves. Such problems urgently demand solutions adequate to their systemic character (p. 49).

The only thing I would add to Lenk's list is activist citizens working to solve the problems, not just experts or government and business leaders.

I have recently argued (Durbin, 2009a) that, in my field, the next generation of young philosophers of technology -- including those still in graduate school -- must master one of several fields outside philosophy. To master the philosophy of biotechnology, for example, a student today must know biotechnology, not just in general, but in detail in some specialty such as agricultural biotechnology. Similarly for computer and information science, for ecology, for medicine, for engineering design, for cultural studies such as film, even for work in such cross-disciplinary fields as science, technology, and society (for example, on the issue of globalization).

Some of the critics claim that academic scholarship has nothing to offer to the solution of real-world problems, that academics are mostly interested in their own inbred concerns, possibly more than anything, their own next promotion. This stands in opposition to those who say that the arts and humanities and social sciences are the last best hope of civilization in today's world. I do not here want to take sides in such a dispute, though I would certainly agree that much that passes for scholarship in the universities, not only in the professional disciplines but also in the arts and humanities, seems often to be merely technical and does not meet the needs of society, let alone provide the vision that is needed. In my view, both a fragmented university of non-communicating specialized disciplinary

communities and a university doing nothing more than turn out specialized technicians for careers in high-tech industries and government agencies represent a serious threat to the traditional ideal of the university.

Whether or not the old ideal is still feasible, the traditional university (going all the way back to the Middle Ages in the West) was expected to serve the human community in more ways than by generating esoteric journal articles and training career-oriented technicians. I would say that its primary mission was to contribute to the cultural life of the community.

How might we be able, in today's world, to bring this about?

An Activist Constituency for Change

In my field of philosophy of technology, I added the following to my call (Durbin, 2009a) to get involved across disciplinary lines. My activist philosophy of technology approach would say that we don't just need the next generation of philosophers of technology to be competent in related fields. We need for them to be improvers of those fields. And one way of doing so is to devote themselves in an activist fashion not only to learning new knowledge in those fields, and to improving future society by applying that knowledge, but also in terms of getting the various professional societies associated with the specialties they are studying to contribute more effectively to a better world for all.

In my philosophical career, I have practiced what I preach; I have worked for a long time in an interdisciplinary program called the Center for Energy and Environmental Policy, where I have worked with graduate students who have been successful in melding their doctoral thesis work, under the slogan of sustainability, with activism to promote improvements in their communities all over the world. Sustainability may run the risk of becoming an empty slogan. But the right kind of sustainability-related graduate education, if joined with real-world progressive activism, can have good consequences for our troubled world. In my article on the topic (Durbin, 2009b), I cite over a dozen examples, from India to Africa to Costa Rica to the Philippines, but here I prefer to highlight just one.

Shih Jung Hsu's doctoral thesis, "Environmental Protest, the Authoritarian State, and Civil Society: The Case of Taiwan" (1995) is my example. As Hsu recognizes, Taiwan has commonly been touted as an economic miracle because of its rapid economic growth over the last three decades. But the Taiwanese state has been willing to sacrifice the natural environment for its spectacular economic growth. In recent years, popular protest has emerged in different communities to challenge the state's single-minded economic development policy. A new civil society emerged in the late 1980s and early 1990s, pressing the government to take action against widespread environmental pollution.

Hsu's dissertation focuses on petrochemical-based pollution in one metropolitan area, Kaohsiung. It examines three polluted communities as case studies of collective action. Hsu identifies three major factors as explaining the emergence of Taiwan's environmental movements: (1) a collective sense of violation by the state-industry pro-growth alliance with a corresponding lack of belief in

mainstream politics as an effective form of redress; (2) a strengthening of community identity and its use to mobilize residents; and (3) political opportunities created by the state's relaxation of authoritarian controls. In Taiwan, activism is still not easy. But after graduation, Hsu returned to Taiwan to begin a professorship, and he has continued to work with the activists he studied.

I think that my experience in that program is generalizable. Graduate programs in engineering, for example, or biomedical ethics, environmental ethics, applied ethics generally, even in philosophy of technology (in the few cases where such programs exist) could, if managed appropriately, train both competent scholars and activists dedicated to the solution of urgent technosocial problems. The problems will certainly never be solved by graduate student efforts alone, but appropriately humble professors can contribute their support to the graduate students and to related activist groups that might possibly be able to do something about these problems.

In arguing for this view, I am being what I might call a pragmatic pragmatist, an activist for social and political causes, and I claim to do so as a philosopher and not just as a citizen. I find that approach best exemplified in the work of the American Pragmatist philosopher, G. H. Mead, who practiced his activism in the social turmoil of the largely immigrant city of Chicago in the first decades of the twentieth century. (See Andrew Feffer's *The Chicago Pragmatists and American Progressivism* (1993); also, on Mead, Carreira da Silva (2011))

Mead was a friend and colleague of the equally activist John Dewey, who moved on from Chicago to be active on the national scene in the USA. But when he was still in Chicago, Dewey's wife Alice -- with his active as well as theoretical support -- ran what was popularly known as the Lab School. It was built on the principles Dewey had been working out in his educational philosophy, and the central feature was experiential learning. Here are two different accounts of the venture.

Robert Westbrook, in *John Dewey and American Democracy* (1991), says this:

In [Dewey's Lab School] one can see not only how the child's interest in a particular activity of his own ([for example] building a model farm) served as the foundation for instruction in a body of subject matter (skills in measurement and the mathematics of fractions) but also how this method introduced children to the methods of experimental problem-solving in which mistakes were an important part of learning. Providing children with firsthand experience with problematic situations largely of their own making was the key to Dewey's pedagogy (p. 103).

Westbrook (1991) then quotes Dewey:

Until the emphasis changes to the conditions which make it necessary for the child to take an active part in the personal building up of his own problems and to participate in methods of solving them (even at the expense of experimentation and error) mind is not really freed (p. 103).

And Westbrook (1991) goes on, later in his book, to link such experiential learning to adults as well as schoolchildren, in adults' efforts to learn, from their own work experiences, as well as from their dissatisfaction with politics as usual, to try to improve their lives and the society in which they live.

Jay Martin, in *The Education of John Dewey* (2003), offers a different perspective on the same material. His book shows how Dewey himself was learning new things all his life, just as he was advising teachers how to help their students -- whether children or adult learners -- to do the same. Repeating some of what Westbrook says, Martin (2003) emphasizes this:

A child in Dewey's school was instantly a member of a cooperative commonwealth. Learning and creating knowledge were merely two forms of knowing, what Dewey called 'methods of life.' From occupations, students in Dewey's school proceeded naturally to their correlatives in the so-called disciplines: from production to economics; from cooperation to politics; from experiment to science; from activity in a community . . . to history, social studies, geography, and culture (p. 200).

Martin (2003) echoes Westbrook in further emphasizing lifelong learning and education for citizenship.

This conception is based on the American Pragmatists' view of the nature of citizenship within a democracy -- the ideal pattern of which they saw exemplified in the ideas of the so-called Founding Fathers of the United States of America, in the Declaration of Independence and the American Constitution, including its amendments over the two subsequent centuries. It is an ideal of citizen involvement in their own governance, far more than just voting; in President Abraham Lincoln's phrase, "government of the people, by the people, and for the people."

Conclusion

Is it possible today to achieve these lofty goals within higher education? (I assume a focus on the USA, but the goals are recognized worldwide.) I would say that the current situation is not likely to change very much unless there is a radical change that I don't see much in evidence. Educational reformers, up to the present, have been active mostly within their own institutions. There has not been citizen activism at a level necessary to bring about the desired changes, even where publicity or government documents have been employed to awaken the general public to the enormity of the problems. In my opinion, educational reformers will never succeed without an enlightened public constituency for educational change of a fundamental sort. It may be too much to ask educational reformers to go out and create a constituency for change. But if they don't do so, and if the right sort of constituency does not develop on its own or as a result of external pressures, it seems likely that fundamental educational reform will remain largely peripheral -- located within a few precarious interdisciplinary programs within particular institutions. Educational establishments, at whatever level, from early grades to institutions of higher learning, may adopt new programs for awhile. But demands for an integrative core of humanities-based studies aimed at training for

citizenship, for leadership, are likely to continue to appear to be peripheral to the perceived main task of pushing a majority of children through secondary school (in many countries, that alone would be a major achievement) and of preparing university students for technical careers.

Still, I remain optimistic. I hope that the needed reformers will come forth, and that a public constituency for fundamental reform in higher education will emerge. If not, I see no hope of solving the crisis. (I am assuming that some people will agree with me that there is a crisis in the first place.)

A final note: This paper is an adaptation and expansion of the concluding part of chapter 4 of my *Social Responsibility in Science, Technology, and Medicine* (Durbin 1992). It thus reflects the crisis 20 years ago, from the perspective of a humanist. But the situation has only worsened in the intervening years, as universities throughout the world receive lower and lower shares of governmental support during times of economic crisis, and thus implicitly less popular support. It has been recently updated to reflect new scholarly input on the issues.

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Notes on Contributors

Paul T Durbin, PhD, is an Emeritus Professor in the University of Delaware Philosophy Department and Center for Energy and Environmental Policy, College of Human Resources, Education, and Public Policy. Dr. Paul T Durbin is retired from the Philosophy Department and the Center for Energy and Environmental Policy of the University of Delaware (USA) in 2004. Dr. Durbin had taught engineering ethics for over 10 years and taught medical ethics, including medical students at Jefferson Medical College in Philadelphia and resident physicians at Christiana Care Medical Center in Delaware for another 10 years. He was a founding member of the Society for Philosophy and Technology, president from 1997 to 1999, long-time editor of the society's publications, and wrote a history of the first 30 years of the society: "Philosophy of Technology: In Search of Discourse Synthesis" (2007; in *Techne* 10:2, available online at spt.org, journals - but only for SPT members). He has published over two dozen other books and numerous articles in professional journals, mostly on the social responsibilities of professionals in all fields. Contact e-mail address is: pdurbin@udel.edu

EUROPEAN JOURNAL of **SOCIAL BEHAVIOUR**

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ISSN 2408-0292